

Listing of Programs for Physics of the Tropical Atmosphere and Tropical Cyclones

The original programs listed here were created mostly using MATLAB and are presented in the order in which they occur in the book. Over time, we hope to create versions in other languages and this list will be updated accordingly, so if you do not see a version you can use it might be worth checking back later. If you would like to contribute a version in another language (e.g. python) please contact the author at emanuel@mit.edu. You will be credited here and in the program listing.

Name	Link	Description	Language or operating system
RCEpak (Single-column model)	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10795221	Full-up MIT single column model with interactive convection and radiation	FORTTRAN, with MATLAB graphics
Single-column model	http://rcmodel.mit.edu/advanced.html	Online version of the MIT single-column model	N/A
Scripts for retrieving and plotting atmospheric soundings	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10795293	Three main scripts that retrieve and analyze atmospheric soundings	MATLAB
<i>agg.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10800835	Solves equations (3.94) and (3.95) in the text	MATLAB
<i>HadleyPak</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10815377	Simulates 2-D Hadley circulations	FORTTRAN, with MATLAB graphics
<i>Walker.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10825247	Simple Walker Circulation model	MATLAB
<i>Matsuno.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10843630	Plots eigenfunctions of the Matsuno equations	MATLAB
<i>Gill.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10844820	Plots solution to the Gill system for the steady response to imposed SST anomalies	MATLAB

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<i>GillD.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10845301	Time-dependent model for Gill response including drag	MATLAB
EquaPak	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10888602	Eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of the linear equation (7.10)	MATLAB
<i>Steady_state_model.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10936382	Simple steady-state tropical cyclone model	MATLAB
<i>PBLSlabModel.m</i>		Slab boundary layer model	MATLAB
<i>Time_dependent_model.m</i>	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10956451	Simple time-dependent tropical cyclone model	MATLAB
Hurricane.zip	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10957525	Nonhydrostatic, axisymmetric hurricane model of Rotunno and Emanuel (1987)	FORTRAN with MATLAB graphics
<i>fast.m</i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14244053	Algorithm for time-marching equations (14.31) and (14.32) in the text	MATLAB
Tropical Cyclone Risk Model	https://github.com/linjonathan/tropical_clone_risk	Complete TC risk model for downscaling TCs from reanalyses and GCMs	Python